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Edith Stein: Empathy as a Problem. Phenomenology and Personalism

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Abstract

Edith Stein's *On the Problem of Empathy* (1917), together with Max Scheler's *Formalism in Ethics and Non-Formal Ethics of Values* (1916), constitutes the first (German) source of personalism. Both of them would extend and modify Husserl's first words – and would ethically accomplish the project of an intersubjectivity not only made of constitution (aiming at the world – *viser le monde*), but also of relations and values (judging the world). Yet this first work of Edith Stein remains highly phenomenological. The question of the continuity and/or discontinuity of Edith Stein's own journey raises the question of the agreement and/or disagreement between phenomenology and personalism. Can one truly found a “personalism”, and therefore an axiomatic, upon the “phenomenological” method called reduction? To what extent can the phenomenological epoché – which precisely puts “everything” except for the ego (Ideen I, § 57) within brackets, including God and even the set of values (Ideen I, § 58) – truly move to personalism without leaving phenomenology itself? The reflection proposed here on the problem of empathy in Edith Stein is but a stone in the road. However, it legitimates the figure of Husserl's assistant as the one from whom everything starts to play out. Beyond Edith Stein, and through her, phenomenology and personalism begin either to merge or to confront each other, and such is the disputatio that must now be reinitiated.

Keywords: Phenomenology, personalism, empathy, intersubjectivity, Edith Stein, Max Scheler

Edith Stein's *On the Problem of Empathy* (1917), together with and following Max Scheler's *Formalism in Ethics and Non-Formal Ethics of Values* (1916), constitutes, strictly speaking, the first (German) source of personalism – a notion that already appears in the title of Max Scheler's complete work: *New Essay on the Foundation of Ethical Personalism*. Both of them would extend and modify Husserl's first words – and would ethically accomplish the project of an intersubjectivity not only made of constitution (aiming at the world – *viser le monde*), but also of relations and values (judging the world). The fact is that this first work of Edith Stein – *On the Problem of Empathy* (1917) – which precedes by more than fifteen years her philosophical anthropology course on *The Human Person*, which she delivered in Münster (1932-1933), remains highly phenomenological. Can one thus truly found a “personalism”, and therefore an axiomatic, upon the “phenomenological” method called reduction? In other words, to what extent can the phenomenological epoché – which precisely puts “everything” except for the ego (Ideen I, § 57) within brackets, including God and even the set of values (Ideen I, § 58) – truly move to personalism without leaving phenomenology itself?

This is not simply a question of phenomenological orthodoxy, but of the possible or impossible continuity of two modes of thought which, in their struggle at reconciling with each other, might well appear separated rather than connected. The question of the continuity and/or discontinuity of Edith Stein's own journey – from her position as Husserl's assistant lecturer (1917) to that of pedagogy teacher (1932) and to Sister Benedicta of the Cross (1934) – goes beyond the simple case of the saint, however exemplary. This life, or the unity of “her” life, raises the question of the agreement and/or disagreement between the two

approaches – phenomenology and personalism – and it is not certain whether they can be easily reconciled or whether they can be reconciled at all. Karol Wojtyła’s thesis, Reevaluation of the Possibility of Founding a Catholic Ethic on the Ethical System of Max Scheler (1959) is, if not a proof, at least a sign thereof: “The ethical system constructed by Max Scheler is not at all suitable for the scientific formulation of Christian ethics”, the future Pope John Paul II underlined briefly. “In his system, Scheler has deliberately cancelled out the normative character of ethical acts, and there resides the comprehensible consequence of detaching values from the activity of the person.”¹

*Thus, here lies at least a debate if not even a struggle. Moving from “phenomenology” to “personalism” gives rise to a consequence that is not necessarily good: hence the reluctance of both Edmund Husserl and Martin Heidegger to make the double personalist turn – a Catholic one in fact – of Max Scheler and Edith Stein. The question therefore deserves to be asked again today with a new force: “on what ground and in what way can one found a ‘phenomenological ethics’ without anchoring it necessarily upon an apriorically given axiomatic, but a descriptivity mode based upon the ethos as a behaviour or as a way of being in the world rather than upon ethics in the sense of an a priori norm to be searched for?”² The reflection proposed here on the problem of empathy in Edith Stein is but a stone in the road. However, it legitimates the figure of Husserl’s assistant as the one from whom everything starts to play out. Beyond Edith Stein, and through her, phenomenology and personalism begin either to merge or to confront each other, and such is the disputation that must now be reinitiated – hence On the Problem of Empathy (*Zum Problem der Einfühlung*), the thesis of Husserl’s young doctoral student, with which everything started.*

Introduction: The Problem of Empathy

“But I, too, had naturally regarded the whole [of this work] as a blueprint that I wanted to realise throughout my life.”³ This formulation of Edith Stein’s, found in a letter to Ingarden dated 27 April 1917, thus consecrated her first essay, her thesis *On The Problem of Empathy (Zum Problem der Einfühlung)*, as the programmatic core from which the future of her thought was to expand. If “during his remarkable lecture on nature and mind” Husserl had indeed said that “an objective external world could only be apprehended intersubjectively”, the notion that he later referred to as *Einfühlung* – his assistant would later confess in *The Life of a Jewish Family* (1933) – “he did not explain what it actually was”.⁴ Thus, *On the Problem of Empathy* is a transmutation of “empathy as a problem”, at least in the sense that the young philosopher’s thesis not only repeats the work of the master, but also continues it and even transforms it. The confession that concludes the Foreword of her work is certainly a tribute to the founder of phenomenology, and it is a way of taking a distance from him, too; it also shows in the figure of the disciple the signs of the one who, probably and secretly at the same time, possessed both the claim and the means to becoming herself a master: “the way of posing the problem and the method of my work have been developed entirely, of course, from the suggestions that I received from Professor Husserl, which makes it very difficult to discern, from the ideas that follow, those that I could legitimately claim as my ‘spiritual property’. However, I can say that the results I am now putting forward have been acquired as a result of *my own work*, which I could no longer affirm were I to make any modifications to them now.”⁵

It is clear then that, while the question of the “experience of an individual by other individuals” certainly originated with Husserl, or precisely with Theodore Lipps, its treatment was to be Steinian and not Husserlian, following a kind of phenomenology that was directly intersubjective rather than constitutive: “this *positive* work seemed to me to be equally indispensable so that I could *take a critical stance* on the results that I obtained up to now”, admitted the young assistant. “It is the question of empathy as an *experience of foreign subjects and their lived experience* that I identified as *this* fundamental problem”.⁶

But there are some more and better things than a simple dialogue with the question of empathy and the philosophers who take part in the debate (in particular Husserl, Lipps, and Scheler) in this original work by the young Edith Stein. For, as early as *On the Problem of Empathy*, the question is raised concerning the very status of phenomenology – if not of its limits, at least of its usage. Her thesis, of which only the phenomenological part was published while the historical part was crossed out and even deleted and lost, opens with a real “Discourse on Method” in phenomenology. What we see here is more than a simple synthesis or a mere reworking of *Ideen I*, published a few years earlier (1913); we see a real declaration of principle on what is to be done, or what one ought to do, the moment one must speak of individuals as “foreign subjects” and of their “living” (*vivre, Erleben*). Here arises, within the explicit framework of phenomenology, the question of an authentic encounter between subjects and the possible sharing of their lived experiences (*vécus*): “the attitude we adopt when we do this – i.e. the task of considering the ‘givenness of the other to myself’ – is that of the ‘phenomenological reduction’”.⁷

Thus, as a faithful student to her teacher and thesis supervisor, the young doctoral student opens the very first lines of her first work in good phenomenological line with the epoché or the bracketing of the natural, i.e. objective, attitude. What is at stake here is the credibility of phenomenology itself, its authenticity and also its effectiveness. For if one of the major steps of phenomenology consists for its founder in not remaining at the mere level of egoity, it is still necessary to realise the project that the *Ideen I* or the *Ideas Pertaining to a Pure Phenomenology and to a Phenomenological Philosophy* (1913) have only announced rather than carried out. One had to wait until the fifth of the *Cartesian Meditations* (1927) before this task could be fully accomplished. In this sense, Husserl’s assistant was more than a simple scribe or redactor of a manuscript, which Husserl himself has never published during his lifetime (*Ideen II*). With her thesis on empathy (1917), she drew her master to the side of experience constitution and recovery, which was something that the simple ideality of an aiming (*visée*) of consciousness had not yet anticipated.

Two meanings of the term “phenomenology” coexist ever since the creation of the Göttingen Circle (in 1913) – with which Edith Stein already finds herself at the crossroads: either the ordinary meaning of “phenomenology” as a “descriptive process”, such as the one to be found in Hegel’s *Phenomenology of the Spirit* or in Rudolf Otto’s *The Sacred*, or the rather technical and properly Husserlian meaning of phenomenology in the “reductive” sense, i.e. related to the bracketing of the objectivity of the thing and the return to the act of consciousness that is aiming at it (*Ideen I*). The young doctoral student’s fidelity to the method of the epoché – which is meant to reach not only the lived experiences of my own consciousness but, at the same time, those of other consciousnesses or the consciousness of others – is so clear here that it actually makes one wonder how it was possible for her later to turn towards a certain a priori position of values (personalism) or a certain form of

realism (Thomas Aquinas). Conscious or not, her turn was a crucial one, and one cannot ignore it or one would risk missing precisely what constituted the originality of the young doctoral student's itinerary.

We know this from having heard it many times, and from the Steinians who have often repeated it. While in the past people would accuse Edith Stein of having “broken with phenomenology” in order to reach and develop a “Christian philosophy”,⁸ today there is a tendency that suggests it has found, on the contrary, a solution of continuity. From Husserl to personalism or even to Thomas Aquinas, a new compatibility could be possible today. And this would be a way of satisfying both the camp of phenomenologists – by being rooted in the greatest theological tradition – and the camp of theologians, so as not to get lost in pitfalls or even in the alleged dangers of an all-constituting egoity.

And yet, the question of the said continuity between phenomenology and Christian philosophy deserves to be asked anew, because among certified phenomenologists the figure of Edith Stein is far from being unanimously accepted. Some would reproach her for having simplified things too much, others for constantly theologising everything, others again for not giving enough space to technicalities or for having operated a return to metaphysics that was totally unjustified. In short, if it is appropriate to celebrate “Edith Stein the philosopher” – and there is no doubt about that – the question remains as to what kind of philosophy we are talking about: phenomenology, Aristotelianism, Thomism or San Juanist mysticism? Her ambition, explicitly stated in her beautiful autobiographical Foreword to *Finite and Eternal Being* (1936/1939), namely to “merge medieval thought with contemporary thought”⁹ is not self-evident. This is not to say that medieval philosophy should not be “actualised” (far from it; our own perspective in fact testifies to this),¹⁰ but that the juxtaposition of traditions does not consecrate their fusion. Nothing guarantees us that choosing one side (the Thomistic tradition or personalism) doesn't make us lose the original source of the other side (phenomenology). The return to a certain form of objectivism or axiomatics on the one side could well annihilate all the efforts of the epoché or the phenomenological reduction on the other.

1. Reduction and Objectivity

As we said, and the thesis on empathy could not be clearer on this point, Stein's “method of research is that of the phenomenological reduction”, which means that any attempt at making empathy explicit shall not be based on the “natural attitude”, nor even on “natural experience”: “this is how the whole world around us, the physical as well as the psychological world, the bodies as well as the souls [*Seelen*] of men and animals [...] are subject to the force of bracketing or reduction. What is left when everything has been erased, the whole world and the subject itself who experiences it [...]? my *lived experience of the thing*, which is beyond doubt”.¹¹ This start, which is purely Husserlian even where the donation of the foreign living (*vivre étranger*) is concerned – that is, the other to whom I will never have access in the mode of simple objectivity – thus makes the Steinian thesis purely Husserlian, hence entirely reductive, at least initially. The real divide between Edith Stein and Husserl at this time (1917) does not have to do with some claim to objectivism or personalism, which would only come later in Stein's conversion journey, but in Husserl's own distancing from his disciples rather than his disciples' distancing from him.

Let us be clear here. A sort of “retrospective illusion” invades, in our opinion, Steinian studies and even phenomenology in general, so that one sees a “realistic” turn among Husserl’s disciples, whereas it was probably Husserl himself who, unbeknownst to his first disciples, made an “idealist” turn. His *Logical Investigations* (1901) differ greatly from the *Ideen I* (1913) – which is why many philosophers have discovered him at the University of Halle and then followed him to Göttingen and even Freiburg im Breisgau – in that it is less a question of “reduction” than of “meaning”, of “bracketing the world” than of “filling the intention with intuition”. Hence, “the question of intersubjectivity even appeared as a challenge [for Edith Stein],” Michel Dupuis points out in his introduction to the French version of Stein’s thesis on empathy, “while the ‘realism’ of the first phenomenological works (the famous *Logical Investigations*) seemed to recede in the face of a new ‘transcendental idealism’ as Husserl’s thinking developed its methodological conceptual foundations.”¹² Of course, one may wonder about the application of the term “realism” to *Logical Investigations*, the word’s connotations placing it definitely on the side of Thomistic objectivism rather than on the side of Cartesian subjectivism. But we will at least recognise that, in the descriptivity of meaning in the *Logical Investigations* as well as in the evidence of the donation of meaning including in relation to the other (the sixth “logical investigation”), there is more thickness of meaning than in the reduction imposed in the *Ideen I* – at least in that the subject was less present than the object, in the sense here of its object-hood (*objectité*) rather than its objectivity. In other words, while the *Logical Investigations* insist on the donation of meaning by the thing itself, even if this is being based on the meaning of the sentence, the *Ideen I* refers more to the constitution of this same meaning by the subject, and thus to the transcendental conditions of its reception rather than to the requirements of its production.

This review of the technicalities of the debate has in fact only one end and one purpose: to show it was not Husserl’s disciples that had changed by opposing their master’s transcendental turn; rather, it was the master himself who took a more idealistic path, a path that made his disciples follow him less, if at all. The “retrospective illusion” thus amounts to projecting onto Husserl’s followers, and in particular onto Edith Stein, a transformation that did not belong to them. The so-called and misnamed “phenomenological realism” of Edith Stein or Max Scheler is not opposed to idealism, but rather constitutes its background.

What appears here as a matter for specialists actually involves the very reading of Edith Stein’s *On the Problem of Empathy* and the possibility of understanding this project today. In spite of the “empathic turn” specific to the young doctoral student, what is indeed surprising, if one reads this work well without projecting any retrospective illusion upon it, is precisely the exact proximity of this first opus to the Husserl of the *Ideen* rather than the *Logical Investigations*, i.e. of idealism rather than realism. *On the Problem of Empathy* poses a problem for today’s reception precisely in that one can’t see, or one can no longer see, the problem itself, which, however, “stands there before” (*pro-blema*) the whole classical interpretation of Stein’s philosophical view. A proof of this is the analysis from the beginning of her book on the hallucinatory phenomenon of the sick man who “thought that he noticed a door in the wall” and then recognised his hallucination. For it is not the so-called reality of the door that makes sense here, but rather its object-hood that was born precisely out of the reduction of its objectivity. The “phantasmatic” existence of the door

exists in a different way, or rather in a magnified way, compared to the door itself, at least in the mode of the reduction or the phenomenological epoché: “he does not believe (or no longer believes) that the door exists,” the doctoral student continues, “but he is still capable of transposing himself into the vanished perception [...]. This is how the whole ‘world phenomenon’ remains after the suspension of the world.”¹³ We can see, or at least feel, that the reduction invades the entire field of perception so that we could find it difficult to speak of Edith Stein’s realism in tune with the *Logical Investigations*, like Scheler’s for example, rather than of an idealism in tune with the *Ideen I* published in 1913, the year when the writing of her thesis began.

If the objectivist turn (Thomism) or the axiomatic turn (personalism) were in some way to be freed from the reduction – and we shall return to this later – there is no guarantee that it was taken or even announced, at least at the beginning of the young doctoral student’s journey. Only this common background of a (methodological, at least) continuity from Husserl to Edith Stein at the time when she placed her thesis under his direction explains what one would later call her turn or rather her break from her master. It is by recognising the continuity in *On the Problem of Empathy* [1917] that we can see the later discontinuities gradually become more and more pronounced – in particular in the numerous texts published in French by Philibert Secretan on *Phenomenology and Christian Philosophy* [from 1929 to 1936] – and find their climax in *Finite Being and Eternal Being* [1936]. It is only there, and quite late, that the objectivist turn towards truth in itself (Thomas Aquinas) and the personalist turn towards the quest for values (Max Scheler) are taken.

A number of statements, well known or to be known, mark thus this late and almost definitive separation between the Husserlian transcendental phenomenology on the one hand and the Steinian metaphysical ontology on the other hand. This is the case of her essay on *Husserl and Thomas Aquinas* (1929), which, conceived as a tribute to Husserl’s 70th birthday, rather widened the gap: “the most fundamental difference between transcendental phenomenology and Catholic philosophy is expressed as follows: here a *theocentric* orientation, there an *egocentric* orientation”.¹⁴ Or again – the hint of idealism surprisingly denounced in the figure of Martin Heidegger and his being-in-the-world in “The Meaning of Phenomenology as a Worldview” (1932): “As for the idealist, he is fascinated by the discovery of the part that the subject plays in the constitution of the world and he absolutises it to the point of losing the sense of the dependencies in which the subject finds itself”.¹⁵ And finally, the no less radical opposition between a “Catholic conception” and a “modern conception” of the world (which is the title of the conclusion of the same text), culminating in a passage that is rather scanty in *Finite and Eternal Being* (1936): “but the total detachment of modern philosophy from the revealed truth is serious in its consequences. Modern philosophy no longer sees in the revealed truth an opportunity for checking on its results. Nor does it accept the tasks that theology presented to it, but wishes to solve the difficulties by its own means. [Philosophy] does not only consider it its duty to limit itself to the natural light of reason, but also to avoid going beyond the world of natural experience. It wants to be an autonomous science in the full sense of the word. This tendency has led it to become to a large extent an atheistic science”.¹⁶

Some would argue that in this passage, as in all the others, Edith Stein is not condemning modern philosophy as such as well as all the avatars of Kantianism or transcendentalism that modern philosophy could, according to them, be loaded of. They

would argue, as good judges in times of peace, that she sought rather to reconcile, or as she would have put it herself, to “merge” “modern philosophy” and “Catholic scholastic philosophy”, to make the “philosophy of our time” coincide with the “philosophy of all times” (*philosophia perennis*). Better still, they would show that she was, and still is, in the right line of Husserl, so that she would never have denied the phenomenological tradition in which she was initiated and to which she was committed etc.

But in reconciling too much, one forgets how to read and, at the same time, how to decide. If one cannot accept the hypothesis of a radical break between Edith Stein and phenomenology,¹⁷ one should not oppose to it the hypothesis of a radical and complete continuity either.¹⁸ In reality, everything depends on where one chooses to place one’s cursor when speaking of continuity or rupture. In our opinion, Edith Stein does not leave, and has never left, phenomenology in that the principle of descriptivity has always remained the leitmotiv of her writings and her thought, much more so than in Husserl, as we shall return to in the case of empathy (with the example of the acrobat, which she inherited from Lipps and Scheler). But she was, to say the least, “less phenomenological” starting from her 1921 conversion. Not that phenomenology was incompatible with theology – French phenomenologists have largely proved the opposite (M. Henry, J.-L. Marion, J.-L. Chrétien, J.-Y. Lacoste etc.) – but in that her return to Thomism or personalism can only pull her towards a form of objectivism or axiomatics that is hardly compatible with phenomenology understood in its “reductive” sense even when this turn seems more adequate to the so-called “Catholic” or “Christian” truth.

Edith Stein was a “phenomenologist” before her conversion (reductive phenomenology); she remained one after her conversion (descriptive phenomenology) but according to a meaning of phenomenology that has radically changed this time – from its technical and Husserlian meaning of the *Ideen I* within the framework of a phenomenology of reduction to its broader meaning in the *Logical Investigations* according to the requisite of a phenomenology of donation, or even to its most extended meaning as a “descriptive process” as we have defined it above (Hegel or Rudolf Otto). Initially, Edith Stein was not a disciple of Scheler or Lipps, but of Husserl, including the Husserl of the reduction. She then returned to Scheler or Lipps after having noticed, quite quickly indeed, the limits of the reduction, in order to claim later a certain objectivism of the “Catholic truth”, this time based on the translation of St. Thomas Aquinas’ *De veritate* under the direction of the Jesuit Einrich Przywara. The term “metaphysical phenomenology”, commonly used by commentators in relation to Edith Stein, certainly irritates the vested phenomenologist, who sees precisely a “contradiction” between the objectivity of metaphysics inherited from Aristotle and the subjectivism of phenomenology coming from Descartes, a point where Edith Stein and her disciples see if not a “coincidence” at least a possible “reconciliation”.

Does this mean that *On the Problem of Empathy* only poses the “problem” of the future Carmelite’s rooting in a pure loyalty to Husserl’s reductive phenomenology, so that she would later feel obliged to leave it for the sake of “Truth”, as she put it? Or should one have the interpretation of her first work reduced to the distance between her and her thesis director, which one could already discern here and there? Only a diversion via Empathy itself would permit us the step that we needed to take before we could move forward. The *Einfühlung*, at least as it is developed here, shows in Edith Stein a truly original mode of otherness, which Husserl himself would not adopt as such, thus opening up a

form of personalism that the master's assistant would later claim, perhaps at the risk of leaving him – at least in part.

2. Empathy and Unipathy

As we said, and as Husserl's former assistant would later comment in *Life of a Jewish Family* (1933): "Husserl had said that an objective external world could only be apprehended intersubjectively [...]. He called this experience *Einfühlung* in connection with the work of Theodor Lipps, but he did not explain what it consisted of."¹⁹ In Edith Stein's own eyes, therefore, there would be no break but rather a continuity between her work and Husserl's, at least in her thesis completed under his supervision. As early as *Ideen I* (1913), thus before the publication of Edith Stein's thesis on empathy (1917) and during the very course of its writing, Husserl introduced right in the beginning of his masterpiece the dimension of the other and of the possibility – impossible in reality, or possible asymptotically only – of the encounter with it in its own constitutive lived experiences (*vécus*) [§ 1 : "Natural knowledge and experience"]: "we have an originary experience of ourselves and our states of consciousness in the so-called internal perception or self-perception; we have none of the other and of their experiences in empathy (*Einfühlung* [translated by P. Ricoeur as "intropathy"]). We apperceive the experiences of the other on the basis of the perception of their bodily manifestations. This apperception through empathy (intropathy) is indeed an intuitive and donating act, but no longer an originally donating act."²⁰ As we have said, only the fifth *Cartesian Meditation* would accomplish Husserl's programme, drawing it more towards the "analogical grasp of the other" (more conceptual and constitutive) than towards "empathy" (still too affective or sentimental in Husserl's eyes, at least at that time).

Taking up precisely this idea of an "apperception by empathy" of the other that can never be fully realised, Edith Stein then gave substance to it in her thesis, developing it by examples on the one hand, and marking her own departure from Theodor Lipps and even from Max Scheler on the other hand.

(a) Let us see first the examples: the example of pain, of course, but also the example of joy. "A friend comes to me and tells me that he has lost his brother and I perceive his pain. What is then this apperception?"²¹ What I see, the doctoral student points out, is not "the external perception of pain". His defeated face will certainly tell me *that* he is suffering, but not *how* he is suffering. While my own experiences are given to me in an originary way (because I live them and I am for myself the only subject who fully experiences them), those of others are only given to me in a non-originary way, transposed or presentified, in a way that never gives me access to the suffering of the other - yet they nevertheless make me present there by my experience without being present there by his situation: "in empathy, it is again a matter of an act that is originary, a present experience (*vécu*), but which is non-originary in its content [...]. When the other suddenly appears before me, he stands in front of me (the sadness, for example, that I read on the other's face); but when I follow the implicit tendencies (that I try to bring myself to a clear donation of the mood in which the other is), he is no longer strictly speaking an object, but he has drawn me *into him*. Now I am no longer turned *towards him*, but rather turned *in him* towards his object, I am close to his subject in his own place. And it is only after a

certain clarification has taken place in this fulfilment that he stands in front of me again as an object”.²²

Edith Stein’s descriptive power appears here with brilliance. We are far from the many programmes of description commonly demanded by Husserl yet never realised with a few rare exceptions (especially in *Ideen II*). In the experience of empathy with others, as in the case of the phenomena of “recollection”, “expectation” and “imagination”, which Husserl also refers to as Edith Stein points out,²³ the originary arises as non-originary (the recollection of a past feeling, for example, which I relive, although I do not experience it, based on an intended object that is present here as “flesh and blood”), but referring to an originary (i.e. the past situation in which I lived and which we could still share). Hence “the joy of the other that springs up in him is an originary joy” adds the young phenomenologist who thus moves beyond the problems of pain and suffering, “although I myself do not experience it as originary”.²⁴

(b) The objects analysed or described here (the non-originary originary-ness of accessing the suffering or the joy of others) then mark the divide between Edith Stein and Theodor Lipps, or even between her and Max Scheler this time. As far as Lipps is concerned, this is well known. Empathy can be complete, so that “there is no separation between one’s own self and the foreign self, which are both one thing”.²⁵ Such an interpretation of the giving (*donné*) of the phenomenon would then make it possible to see and to think that I could totally adopt the kinestheses of the other not only in his sensations but also and above all in his affects: “I am *one (eins)* with the acrobat, in whose movements I participate inwardly by looking at her”. By imitation or by complete identification, I would then wrongly believe “myself” to be the acrobat, not in her identity but at least in her effectiveness. Her movements would be identically my movements, her pain my pain, her joy my joy, in that a complete participation in the other would be authenticated here. This is the famous error of Lipps, in the eyes of Stein of course, but also of Husserl (who analysed it less) and of Max Scheler, too, who precisely quoted and made use of Edith Stein herself in the second version of *Nature of Sympathy* (1923): “I am not one with the acrobat,” says Stein: “I am only attached to her.”²⁶ *Einfühlung* (empathy or intropathy) is not *Einsfühlung* (affective fusion or unipathy). The specificity of the relationship with the other is that one cannot and will not merge with him or her in such a way as for one to disappear.

What is given and said here from the point of view of pure and simple phenomenology (*On the Problem of Empathy*, 1917) will not be without consequences for theology (*Finite and Eternal Being*, 1936) and mysticism (*The Science of the Cross*, 1941). From the first [*On the Problem of Empathy*], we shall retain that individuality cannot be considered without community, from the point of view of man as well as God: “the double meaning of the term humanity, which is used sometimes for general human nature, sometimes to designate the living whole, corresponds to a double relationship of the individual to humanity: God is the incarnation of the general and a member of the whole”.²⁷ The empathy of men in God (humanity) is also gained through the empathy of God to men (community), making the mystical body the very place of the link between the monads or the individuals unified by it.

Of the second [*The Science of the Cross*], it will be noted that the mystical marriage of bridegroom and bride in the *Sermon on the Song* finds its philosophical justification precisely in such a phenomenological mode of empathy. God himself and only he, in a double

interpretation inherited from St. Bernard of Clairvaux and St. John of the Cross, manages to fully realise empathy or the community of experiences (*Einfühlung*) without, however, falling into the flaw or drifting of the affective fusion or unipathy (*Einsfühlung*). His Trinitarian nature allows him to differentiate himself, in an indissoluble unity that allows us, too, to share what is experienced in him. To live the life of Christ – “it is no longer I who live, but Christ who lives in me” (Gal 2:20) – is not or no longer simple *imitatio Christi* or *sequela Christi* but properly speaking *experientia Christi*, that is to say, the sharing of experiences by which we are both dispossessed and transformed: “the soul that has reached mystical marriage finds itself in the inner cell of the Beloved, that is to say, in the supreme degree of love... By submitting their will perfectly to that of God, men (saints) also give our Lord the possibility of disposing of them as members of his Mystical Body. They no longer live their own life, but Christ’s; they no longer suffer their own pain, but Christ’s. For this reason, they also rejoice in the life of grace, which the Lord kindles in other souls in the hours when the spark of divine love touches them and the wine of that love plunges them into a blessed intoxication.”²⁸

We can see it. While a solution of discontinuity or at least of non-radical continuity could be envisaged from the reductive phenomenology (1917) to the substantial metaphysics (1929-1936) via the stage of the conversion (1921), a complete continuum can and must also be established from the *Thesis on Empathy* to the *Mysticism of the Cross* – in our view, not in the mode of reduction this time, but in the mode of divine-human empathy as a condition of human-divine empathy and of men among themselves. If personalism can, or could, remain a thread running through the whole of Edith Stein’s work, it would be rooted less in the phenomenological epoché – which she would never cease to leave or to accuse of hints of idealism – than in the experience of empathy, which makes it possible for each person to feel, at least in part, what the other feels (*Einfühlung*), without nevertheless ever “fusing” with this other experience (*Einsfühlung*). With the other, and in God, I discover a unity that in and of myself I could not produce, so that from the divine persons (the Father, the Son, and the Holy Spirit) to the human persons (the other), the consequence is good. It is because we are in God that we also receive from the Trinity what makes up our personality.

The conviction is clear, at least when reading and going through the whole of Edith Stein’s journey. Her thesis and then her book *On the Problem of Empathy* certainly makes empathy “a problem” as soon as one considers the relationship of reduction (*Ideen I*) to objectivity or rather to the filling of meanings (*Logical Research*). But it finds its solution, or rather its fulfilment, in a “living with” or in a “community of lived experiences” (*Einfühlung*) as soon as it extends theologically to the whole of humanity (*Finite and Eternal Being*) and mystically to the body of Christ himself (*The Science of the Cross*). If the phenomenological epoché or the reduction does not work, or if it acts less, in the works subsequent to *On the Problem of Empathy* where it still played its part to the full, the fact is that what she wanted or sought to achieve remains, and always will: a pure self, or a “core of the soul” (*Kern der Seele*), taking the “living” and “feeling alive” and making it the irreducible heart of an individuality capable of constituting itself: “the being of the soul, like the core (*Kern*) in which it is rooted, is something individual, indissoluble, and ineffable.”²⁹

3. The Irreducible Life

On the Problem of Empathy of 1917 is the definitive statement of a reductive phenomenology, or rather of a reinterpretation of the epoché in the sense of an act that Husserl himself had not been able to formulate to this extent, and for which one would have to wait for Michel Henry's radical phenomenology before one could see it recovered: "I must therefore put the position of existence (*Existenz-Setzung*) out of action, as I cannot make any use of it; but what I cannot put out of action and what is beyond doubt is *my living of the thing* [...] along with its correlate, the complete *thing-phenomenon* [...]"³⁰ The Husserlian noetic-noematic correlate is here clearly affirmed, though oriented differently. Where Husserl distinguished the layers of the experiences of consciousness like so many strata according to their respective aims (*visées*), Edith Stein reached, as Michel Henry would do later, the "living" (*vivre*) itself, and not only the lived experiences (*vécus*). Hence the fact that *her* path, eminently reductive in *The Problem of Empathy*, was not identical to *the* path of Husserl himself as he traced it in *Ideen I* and in his later works. Better still, if my "living" is not identified with a simple sum or stratum of my own experiences, then the same is true of the other, who is no longer reduced to his or her own experiences or kinestheses, but to a substratum of the "living" (*vivre*), which also makes its life in him or her: "the world in which I live is not only a world of physical bodies; there are also in it, in addition to myself, other *living subjects*, and I *know something* about this living"³¹ The "knowing about the living of others", whether it be related to "widespread and localised sensations" (pleasure, tickling, itching, etc.), "vital feelings" (weariness of the body, strong or weak sensation of life, calm and tension etc.), "psychic feelings" (grief, sadness, melancholy etc.), or "religious feelings of a metaphysical nature" (beatitude, despair, security of the soul, remorse, peace and security etc.), to take up the hierarchy of feelings established by Max Scheler in *The Meaning of Suffering*, is certainly not directly accessible as a particular and singular living (*vivre*). Better still, this is paradoxically all the more foreign, and therefore all the less sharable, because it is more attached to corporeality (tickling or itching) than to spirituality (mourning, sadness, bliss or despair). The fact remains that it belongs to a sphere of living that is also mine, or is likely to become mine, and that in this way it constitutes the form or the substratum of the unity of our experiences.³²

According to Husserl's disciple, there are three possible ways for my lived experience (*vécu*) to meet the lived experience of others – and to constitute each of us as well as our community: (a) the way of the physical body, (b) the way of consciousness, (c) and the way of the concrete lived experiences of each individual. But Edith Stein does not retain any of them, as if the unity of the "incarnate life" had to be given immediately in the meeting of the experience of others as a "foreign living". (a) "We could start from the concrete phenomenon" as both "physical body" and "living and perceiving body", but this first hypothesis, taken from Husserl's *Ideen II*, whose manuscript Edith Stein rereads – a hypothesis later relayed by Merleau-Ponty and Gabriel Marcel – could not, in her opinion, be validated in that it still started from egoity alone, even if it was incarnate. (b) "We could (then) investigate how everything that appears beyond the simple physical body given in external perception is constituted from the point of view of consciousness", but this second path opened up by *Ideen I* is also blocked here because it dissociates soul from corporeality. (c) "We could, moreover, consider the concrete and particular lived

experiences [*Erlebnisse*] of these individuals”, but here again this route inherited from Lipps is unusable, in that it separates individuals into monads and then makes them meet each other, which is not a true form of otherness. This leaves one with “the” path, the only one – that of the “irreducible or foreign living” – which leads the doctoral student towards what she calls “another more radical consideration”, which is still “possible”: (d) “all these donations of the *foreign living* refer to a fundamental species of acts, in which foreign living is grasped and which we now want to define [...] as empathy”.³³

This point is important, at least in our eyes, in that this Steinian consideration of “foreign living” in empathy (*Einfühlung*) allows her figure to escape from a certain form of irenicism that is sometimes attributed to her, at least in the layering of a cosmos so unified and oriented that nothing of the nonsensical can remain, if not in the ineffable zone of an apophatism always related to the divinity. There is more, and better, in Edith Stein, at least in the first period of her thesis on empathy, than the idea of a world that is always already given, in an immediate recognition of the created that makes her discourse escape pure and simple humanity. The philosopher Edith Stein – as a philosopher – does not perform at all as a theologian in the hour of empathy and even though, as she herself admits, certain events in her life could already have led her towards spirituality (particularly her meeting with Max Scheler and her reading of his books): “I, the living subject (*erlebende*) who considers the world and my own person as a phenomenon,” writes the young doctoral student in an accent that today we would find rather Henrian or Merleau-Pontian, “am *in the living* and only *in it*, and as unmistakable and ineffable as itself.”³⁴

If there is an ideal of transparency, everything is held, including perhaps in Edith Stein, and at least in her early work, in the obscure background of an existence and of our own existence. This is certainly teleological, and the final seems to take precedence over the initial as the work of the philosopher progresses towards God. But this teleological dimension is first rooted in a protological one, which is made not only of seeds waiting to bloom according to the beautiful considerations of ethics and education, but also of a primordial obscurity that constitutes our pure and simple humanity. If one tried too hard to build up – according to the Steinian personalist turn – one might forget what it is about this chaos that also never ceases to cross us. The relational (the person) cannot receive its true meaning independently of the “foreign living” – which is itself impossible to communicate – or even of the gap that one is to oneself and for oneself, to which it always remains difficult to gain access (the chaos). Phenomenology is, in our view, the foundation of personalism, yet not by virtue of the blissful appearance of the phenomenon, but by the “strangeness” that one is to oneself and to the other before one can even access it.

4. The Problem of Finitude

The “problem of empathy” is then replaced by what we would call the “problem of finitude”. The consideration of the thickness of “finitude” is indeed a real thorn in the flesh in Edith Stein’s relationship this time with her fellow disciple Martin Heidegger – and perhaps in her relationship to the whole of phenomenology, at least as it was received and deployed in France since the post-war period. In her considerations on *Martin Heidegger’s Existential Philosophy* (a text from 1936), the Carmelite could not be clearer, in an attitude that she herself calls “taking a stand”. If finitude can, or could, designate the “fundamental

constitution of man”, as Stein underlines it by taking up and commenting on the famous text from *Kant and the Problem of Metaphysics*, it will no longer mark “the blocked horizon of existence” (Heidegger) but “the necessity of not being *per se* (by oneself) nor *a se* (in oneself), but *ab alio* (by another), a necessity that stems from the fact that man is *something* but not *everything*. Is this not precisely the *proper meaning of finitude?*”³⁵

Certainly, this formula is fascinating, and it has indeed been commented on many times by Steinians as a way of indicating that the Carmelite did not leave finitude and thus a certain modern form of phenomenology, but only transformed its meaning. The problem comes, however, from the fact – which Edith Stein agrees with and whose meaning she purposefully produces – that she relates finitude this time to the *ens creatum*, or created being – which Martin Heidegger, in this very text, has just rejected, in order at least to avoid presupposing right away anything about humanity that was already given initially and historically. To say with Edith Stein that the sense of finitude must be understood as “being something and not everything” (*ibid.*), it is to presuppose on the one hand that, to Martin Heidegger, man “is everything”, and that he “takes on everything”, and on the other hand that finitude is finally not, or no longer, finitude since it is directly referred to the infinite: “*ens creatum* refers not only to an effectively created being, but, because of its finitude, to a being essentially conditioned by the infinite” (*ibid.*). An interpretation that is, let us say, not self-evident simply by reading *Being and Time*, as “finitude” does not refer to any kind of totality or totalization in Martin Heidegger, but only to the horizontality of man’s being-there, making the authenticity of Dasein a place of heroism that probably needs to be fought, yet not finitude as such. Identifying “finitude” with “fallibility”, which is commonly practised in its theological reinterpretation, loses in some way what it originally designated – not “fragility”, but “the fact of facticity” or the “simple fact of being-there”, as Emmanuel Lévinas very accurately and justly interpreted it in *Totality and Infinity*: “To be me, an atheist, at home, separated, happy, created – these are synonyms”.³⁶

Conclusion: The Basic Option

Precisely here in this consideration of the finitude and in its type of interpretation we are probably touching the neuralgic point that separates Edith Stein, in her double personalist and Thomist turn, from her true phenomenological point of departure, where she was more inclined to the “foreign living” than to the “experienced Infinite”. There is good reason, and there was good reason indeed, for Husserl’s young assistant to hold on first to our pure and simple humanity, even if it were then to convert it and morph it into God himself. But this was not the path she chose to take, most certainly because of the radical nature of her conversion that had led her to change completely – even to reject the old thing in order to claim the absolutely new one: “*egocentric* orientation” on the side of “transcendental phenomenology” and “*theocentric* orientation” on the side of “Catholic philosophy”, to use the symptomatic formula of her text on “Husserl and Thomas Aquinas” (1929).³⁷

A phenomenology, including a Christian or Catholic phenomenology (although such labels can only harm, in our view, both phenomenology and theology), must take, or should have taken, as its starting point the “human being” as it is given here on earth at least today in the framework of a unanimously recognised finitude. A common platform is

necessary, if not to discuss, at least to not escape from that which is ordinary in our humanity. Certainly the believer can, and must, be oriented towards God, certainly the aspiration towards the infinite could well determine all that is finite, certainly we prefer to move through immanence and orient it towards transcendence in order to give it meaning. But the question nevertheless arises: how can we speak of, and begin first of all with, a pure and simple humanity, which was also given to us from the outset, simply in that it was loved by God to the point of having become incarnate? How can we embark onto the spiritual path if it is not rooted in a carnal side, too – not in waiting for conversion but simply in being loved and inhabited? Being “in the living and only in it”, to use the words of the very young doctoral student, is this “living” (*leben, vivre*) first and only, or rather primarily, that of the Arch-Son as the first living being so that one must directly think and see oneself in him and from him (in the line of Michel Henry and a whole section of French phenomenology today that is in fact much closer to Edith Stein than it appears)? Or is this same “incarnate living” also the passionate and impulsive “living” of an obscurity that God certainly inhabits but certainly does not overcome, or at least does not spiritualise?

There is therefore no guarantee, and it is even doubtful, that the Christian can and must always and at this point leave the indefectibly “obscure” and “non-transparent” foundation of our humanity, rooted first of all in a world made of “raw and wild being”, or of “primordial nature”, to put it in the terms of the late Merleau-Ponty. Better still, nothing certifies *a priori* that the subsequent turn towards the “relational” (personalism) or towards “truth” (Thomas Aquinas), was to this extent announced and prepared by the young Edith Stein simply by reading or rereading without “retrospective illusion” her 1917 thesis. In reality, this can only be established *a posteriori*. The “irreducible living” discovered in *On the Problem of Empathy* – “my living is not to be put out of action”³⁸ – would certainly receive new interpretations or inflections, for example in 1936 in *Finite and Eternal Being*. But it is on the double condition, redhibitory in the eyes of Martin Heidegger, of substituting “finite” for “finitude” and “eternity” for “temporality” – that very thing that the philosopher had deliberately forbidden himself in *Being and Time* (1927) and then in *Kant and the Problem of Metaphysics* (1929).

There is no room here for a simple debate, and even less for a fight, between phenomenology on the one hand and personalism and Thomism on the other – three dimensions that Husserl’s assistant would progressively espouse in her own right. It is rather a question of a *fundamental option* or a *choice of starting point*. Nothing would justify one in saying that the question of the “person” or “truth” were outdated today, quite the contrary. And even less so that one should always, necessarily, remain with “finitude”, or even with phenomenology only, as if there were no other kind of future than this single type of thinking. Any orthodoxy always runs the risk of “dogmatising”, for sure in phenomenology, but in personalism or Thomism too.

There could indeed be a tendency today, within Christianity and Catholicism in particular, to take the authors in their entirety as the sole criterion of truth without seeing that they themselves can be interpreted in different ways or confronted with others. The debate then becomes sclerotic and often gets stuck in a repetition that no longer creates anything new. Edith Stein, Maurice Blondel, Henri de Lubac, Simone Weil and many others serve today as a vulgate for Catholicism (and are unfortunately only studied within the framework of Christianity, or nearly). It is as if it were forbidden to discuss them, let

alone challenge them – Paul Ricoeur included. Yet, each one in their own time, they knew how to take decisions and how to open up new trails and they were not content to merely repeat ideas. For one, Edith Stein seemed to guard herself against this risk and she did not hesitate to invoke the Nietzschean eternity against the Heideggerian being-for-death. The authors and the references don't matter as long as they can question us. *Being and Time* is not necessarily right against *Thus Spoke Zarathustra*, and the a priori primacy of phenomenology over Nietzscheanism is not self-evident either. Everything depends on how we interpret them and whether we allow ourselves to be transformed by one text or another. Thus, Edith Stein is quoting and morphing, through eternity, the temporal aim of *Thus Spoke Zarathustra*: “Pain says: disappear. But all voluptuousness wants eternity, it wants a deep, deep eternity”.³⁹

(Translated from French by Marius Ion Bența)

Notes

¹ K. Wojtyła, *Reevaluation of the possibility of founding a Catholic ethic on the ethical system of Max Scheler* [Ocena możliwości zbudowania etyki chrześcijańskiej przy założeniach systemu Maksxa Schelera], habilitation thesis published in 1959 in Polish and translated into Italian in 1980 (there are no other translations or editions in other languages), Italian edition: 232. Quoted in R. Buttiglione, *La pensée de Karol Wojtyła* (1982), Paris, Communio-Fayard, 1984: 91–92. We refer to our commentary, “Voici l’homme” (Les deux discours comme provocation pour la philosophie), in F. Follo, *John Paul II et la culture contemporaine*, Paris, Cerf, 2005: 157–186 (in particular 176–179).

² It is in this sense that we have understood the term “ethics”, in *Ethique du corps épanou*, Paris, Cerf, 2018. In particular 34–38 (“Décrire avant de construire”) and 51–54 (“L’éthique et l’ethos”).

³ E. Stein, “Lettre à Ingarden du 27 Avril 1917”, in *Correspondence I, 1917–1933*, Paris, Ad Solem – Cerf, 2009: 96. Quoted in Bénédicte Bouillot, *Le noyau de l’âme selon Edith Stein, De l’épochè phénoménologique à la nuit obscure*, Paris, Hermann, coll. “De Visu”, 2015: 42. With the following mention (T.N.: translation): “But it is precisely in relation to the notion of value that the notion of core is determined in priority”. (T.N.: English translation: *CWES 12: The Collected Works of Edith Stein*, vol. 12, *Letters to Roman Ingarden*, transl. Hugh Candler Hunt, ICS Publications, Washington D.C., 2014.)

⁴ E. Stein, *Vie d’une famille juive* (1933), Paris, Ad solem – Cerf, 2001: 317. (T.N.: English translation in *CWES 1: Life in a Jewish Family: Her Unfinished Autobiographical Account*, trans. Josephine Koeppl in: *The Collected Works of Edith Stein*. Volume 1, ICS Publications, Washington D.C., 1986.)

⁵ E. Stein, *Le problème de l’empathie (Zum problem der Einfühlung [1917])*, Paris, Ad Solem – Cerf, 2012, Foreword: 14. (T.N.: English translation: *CWES 3: On the Problem of Empathy*, trans. Waltraut Stein, ICS Publications, Washington D.C., 1989.)

⁶ *Ibid.*: 13 (author’s emphasis).

⁷ *Ibid.*: 19 (author’s emphasis).

⁸ Reuben Guilead, *De la phénoménologie à la science de la croix, L’itinéraire d’Edith Stein*, Louvain, Nauwelaerts, 1974, ch. II: 103–136 : “Au-delà de la phénoménologie”

⁹ E. Stein, *L’être fini et l’être éternel, Essai d’une atteinte du sens de l’être [1936]*, Beauvechain (Belgium), Nauwelaerts, 1998, Foreword: 2 (T.N.: translation): “The comparison between Thomistic and phenomenological thought has been sketched out by dealing objectively with this problem (the problem of being). And these two preoccupations, namely the search for the meaning of being and the attempt to merge medieval and contemporary thought, are not only the personal goal of the author of this book, but dominate philosophical life and are felt by many philosophers to be

absolutely necessary” (author’s emphasis). (T.N.: English translation: *CWES 9: Finite and Eternal Being*, trans. K. F. Reinhardt, ICS Publications, Washington D.C., 2002.)

¹⁰ See, for example, *Dieu, la chair et l’autre, D’Irénée à Duns Scotus*, Paris, PUF, 2008.

¹¹ E. Stein, *Le problème de l’empathie*, *op. cit.*: 20. (T.N.: On the Problem of Empathy.)

¹² E. Stein, *Le problème de l’empathie*, *op. cit.*, (Introduction by Michel Dupuis): 7. (T.N.: *On the Problem of Empathy*.)

¹³ E. Stein, *Le problème de l’empathie*, *op. cit.*: 20. (T.N.: *On the Problem of Empathy*.)

¹⁴ E. Stein, “La phénoménologie de Husserl et la philosophie de saint Thomas d’Aquin” (1929), in *Phénoménologie et philosophie chrétienne*, Paris, Cerf, 1987: 31–55 (cit.: 43 [emphasis added]). (T.N.: English version in *CWES 8: Knowledge and Faith*, trans. Walter Redmond, ICS Publications, Washington D.C., 2000.)

¹⁵ E. Stein, “La signification de la phénoménologie comme conception du monde”, *ibid.*: 1–18 (cit.: 16).

¹⁶ E. Stein, *L’être fini et l’être éternel* (1936), *op. cit.*: 11. (T.N.: English translation: *CWES 9: Finite and Eternal Being*, trans. K. F. Reinhardt, ICS Publications, Washington D.C., 2002.)

¹⁷ Cf. R. Guilead, *De la phénoménologie à la science de la croix, L’itinéraire d’Edith Stein*, Louvain, Nauwelaerts, 1974.

¹⁸ P. Schulz, *Edith Steins Theorie der Person*, Munich, Alber, 1994; and Ch. Beauvais “Edith Stein et la modernité”, in *Laval théologique et philosophique* 58/1, 2002: 117–136. On this point, see Bénédicte Bouillot’s accurate clarification, which nevertheless leans more towards the solution of “continuity” rather than discontinuity. Cf. *Le noyau de l’âme selon Edith Stein*, *op. cit.* 470–473 (Epilogue): “L’odyssée steinienne de la réduction”.

¹⁹ E. Stein, *Vie d’une famille juive*, *op. cit.*: 317. (T.N.: English translation in *CWES 1: Life in a Jewish Family: Her Unfinished Autobiographical Account*, trans. Josephine Koeppl in: *The Collected Works of Edith Stein*. Volume 1, ICS Publications, Washington D.C., 1986.)

²⁰ E. Husserl, *Idées directrices pour une phénoménologie, [Ideen I (1913)]*, Paris, Tel Gallimard (trans. P. Ricoeur), 1991, ch. I § 1: “La connaissance naturelle et l’expérience”: 15 [S. 8]. (T.N.: English translation: E. Husserl, *Ideas Pertaining to a Pure Phenomenology and to a Phenomenological Philosophy: First Book: General Introduction to a Pure Phenomenology*, transl. Fred Kersten, *Husserliana: Edmund Husserl — Collected Works*, Vol. 2, Martinus Nijhoff, The Hague, 1982.)

²¹ E. Stein, *Le problème de l’empathie*, *op. cit.*: 23. (T.N.: *On the Problem of Empathy*.)

²² *Ibid.*: 30.

²³ *Ibid.*: 26–29.

²⁴ *Ibid.*: 31.

²⁵ *Ibid.*: 39 (title of the paragraph: “Empathie et unipathie”).

²⁶ M. Scheler, *Nature et forme de la sympathie* [seconde version, 1923], Paris, Petite bibliothèque Payot, 2003: 70. (T.N.: English translation: M. Scheler, *The Nature of Sympathy*, trans. Graham McAleer, Taylor & Francis, London, 2007.)

²⁷ Ed. Stein, *L’être fini et l’être éternel*, *op. cit.*: 503. (T.N.: *Finite and Eternal Being*)

²⁸ E. Stein, *La science de la Croix*, Beauvechin (Belgique), Nauwelaerts, 1998: 289–290. (T.N.: English translation: *CWES 6: The Science of the Cross*, transl. Josephine Koeppl, ICS Publications, Washington D.C., 2002.) For a commentary on this new (theological and mystical) mode of empathy, and thus for our close proximity to Edith Stein on this point, we refer to the *Livre de l’expérience*, D’Anselme de Cantorbéry à Bernard de Clairvaux, Paris, Cerf, 2017, Part 3 (“L’expérience en affect”), § 26: 342–375: “L’empathie amoureuse”.

²⁹ E. Stein, *Individu et communauté (Individuum and Gemeinschaft)*, Part 2 of *Beiträge zur philosophischen Begründung der Psychologie und der Geisteswissenschaften*, in Edith Stein Gestamtausgabe (Herder), 2010, vo. VI: 208. (T.N.: English translation: “Individual and Community”, in *CWES 7: Philosophy of Psychology and the Humanities*, trans. Mary Catharine Baseheart, Marianne Sawicki, ICS Publications, Washington D.C., 2000: 156–326.) On this point, we refer again to Bénédicte Bouillot’s magisterial work, *Le noyau de l’âme, De l’époque phénoménologique à la nuit obscure*, *op. cit.* [Hermann], whose entire text is merely an exegesis of this single formula (cited in “Introduction”: 20).

³⁰ Edith Stein, *Le problème de l’empathie*, *op. cit.*: 20. (T.N.: *On the Problem of Empathy*.)

³¹ *Ibid.*: 21.

³² Cf. Max Scheler, *Le sens de la souffrance*, Paris, Aubier-Montaigne, 1978: 6–9. Text if not taken over, at least inherited, from *Nature et forme de la sympathie* [first version of 1913], Paris, Petite

bibliothèque Payot, 2003, Part I, ch. II: 53–100: “Classification des phénomènes de la sympathie”. With, in particular, the impossibility of sharing the ‘same pain’ as that of the father and mother who lose their child (*ibid.*: 60–62). (T.N.: English Translation: M. Scheler, “The Meaning of Suffering”, in: M.S. Frings, (ed.), *Max Scheler (1874–1928) Centennial Essays*, Springer, Dordrecht, 1974: 121–163.)

³³ Edith Stein, *Le problème de l'empathie*, *op. cit.*: 22–23. (T.N.: *On the Problem of Empathy.*)

³⁴ *Ibid.*: 21.

³⁵ E. Stein, “La philosophie existentielle de Martin Heidegger”, in *Phénoménologie et philosophie chrétienne*, *op. cit.*: 117 (author’s emphasis). (T.N.: English translation: Stein, E., “Martin Heidegger’s Existential Philosophy”, transl. Mette Lebeck, Maynooth Philosophical Papers, vol. 4, 2007: 55–98.)

³⁶ E. Lévinas, *Totalité et infini* (1971), Paris, Biblio-Essais, 1990: 158 [“Jouissance et séparation”]. As for the collusion of finitude and fallibility, and their necessary separation, we refer to our article: “Mal et finitude : dialogue avec Ricoeur et Lévinas”, *Etudes théologiques et religieuses*, vol. 92, April-June 2017 (2017/2): 413–431. (T.N.: English translation: Levinas, E., *Totality and Infinity. An Essay on Exteriority*, Kluwer, Dordrecht, 1961.)

³⁷ *Supra*, note 13.

³⁸ Edith Stein, *Le problème de l'empathie*, *op. cit.*: 21. (T.N.: *On the Problem of Empathy.*)

³⁹ E. Stein, ““La philosophie existentielle de Martin Heidegger””, in *Phénoménologie et philosophie chrétienne*, *op. cit.*: 104 [taken from F. Nietzsche, “Le chant d’ivresse”] (T.N.: English translations: Stein, E., “Martin Heidegger’s Existential Philosophy”, transl. Mette Lebeck, Maynooth Philosophical Papers, vol. 4, 2007: 55–98 and “The Drunken Song” from F. Nietzsche, *Thus Spoke Zarathustra*).